

TSPROTO: Fusing Deep Feature Extraction with Interpretable Glass-Box Surrogate Model for Explainable Time-Series Classification

Szymon Bobek^a, Grzegorz J. Nalepa^a

^a*Faculty of Physics, Astronomy and Applied Computer Science, Institute of Applied Computer Science, and Jagiellonian Human-Centered AI Lab, and Mark Kac Center for Complex Systems Research, ul. prof. Stanisława Łojasiewicza 11, Krakow, 30-348, Poland*

Abstract

Deep neural networks (DNNs) are highly effective at extracting features from complex data types, such as images and text, but often function as black-box models, making interpretation difficult. We propose TSPROTO – a model-agnostic approach that goes beyond standard XAI methods focused on feature importance, clustering important segments into conceptual prototypes—high-level, human-interpretable units. This approach not only enhances transparency but also avoids issues seen with surrogate models, such as the Rashomon effect, enabling more direct insights into DNN behavior. Our method involves two phases: (1) using feature attribution tools (e.g., SHAP, LIME) to highlight regions of model importance, and (2) fusion of these regions into prototypes with contextual information to form meaningful concepts. These concepts then integrate into an interpretable decision tree, making DNNs more accessible for expert analysis. We benchmark our solution on 61 publicly available datasets, where it outperforms other state-of-the-art prototype-based methods and glassbox models by an average of 10% in the F1 metric. Additionally, we demonstrate its practical applicability in a real-life anomaly detection case. The results from the user evaluation, conducted with 17 experts recruited from leading European research teams and industrial partners, also indicate a positive reception among experts in XAI and the industry. Our implementation is available as an open-source Python package on GitHub and PyPi.

1. Introduction

Deep neural networks (DNNs) have demonstrated their superiority in various fields dealing with data modalities that make feature extraction challenging, such as images, text, and time-series data. Their unique ability to automatically extract features has made them the preferred choice for many practical applications where such data modalities exist. However, the features extracted by DNNs are typically encoded in latent spaces, making them difficult for humans to interpret. As a result, it is challenging to control the training and operation of systems based

Email addresses: szymon.bobek@uj.edu.pl (Szymon Bobek), grzegorz.j.nalepa@uj.edu.pl (Grzegorz J. Nalepa)

on such black-box models. The advancement of Explainable AI (XAI) has equipped researchers and developers with powerful tools that greatly enhance that task.

This progress creates the potential to leverage XAI algorithms alongside DNNs enabling the generation of high-quality, higher-level features (i.e. concepts) for use in fully interpretable, glass-box models. The ability to abstract raw data into meaningful concepts is particularly promising for time-series data, where the inherent complexity and multidimensional nature pose significant challenges in the interpretation, even for domain experts.

In our understanding, concepts represent meaningful constructs derived from raw feature values processed by deep neural networks. For these features to be truly valuable, they should be interpretable and understandable, yet current XAI methods primarily focus on attributing importance. This presents a challenge for the interpretation of this type of explanations [1]. We aim to go beyond this by adding granularity to importance-based methods by forming conceptual prototypes that allows to create features that are both comprehensible for humans and effective for machine learning models.

This approach provides a pathway to interpret DNNs without relying on surrogate models, which can be vulnerable to the Rashomon effect [2], and does so in a fully model-agnostic manner. It also offers a framework for fostering better collaboration between humans and machines by translating concepts into levels of abstraction that are meaningful to both. This aligns with recent trends in industrial and other AI applications that emphasize Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence (HCAI), where the focus is on augmenting human decision-making, building trust, and improving usability, rather than replacing human roles.

The general idea of our solution is illustrated in Figure 1. It consists of two main phases. In the first phase, we apply existing feature importance attribution methods, such as SHAP, LIME, Grad-CAM, or others, to identify regions of high importance to the model. These regions are used as masks to segment the raw data into smaller parts, which we refer to as interpretable components (or "concept candidates"), while disregarding areas of low or no importance. Next, the interpretable components are clustered into similar groups, referred to as prototypes, and enriched with contextual information to provide more meaningful descriptions in a step called context aggregation. The output of the context aggregation phase forms a set of concepts. Finally, we use these concepts as features in an interpretable model (in our case, a decision tree), creating a fully transparent model. A visual layer added on top of the decision tree structure allows experts to inspect and understand the model more easily. The method has been released under the MIT license as a Python package and is available both in raw source code on GitHub and for instant installation via PyPi ¹.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an overview of existing XAI methods, positioning our research within the taxonomy of current solutions and formally defining the problem. Section 3 introduces our proposed solution, followed by its evaluation in Section 4, which includes tests on 64 benchmark datasets, a real-world example, and an anonymous user study. The study participants were recruited from leading European research centers and companies operating in Industry 4.0 domains. Section 5 discusses the limitations of the proposed approach and outlines directions for future research, while Section 6 concludes the paper with a summary.

¹For source code visit: <https://github.com/sbobe/tspoto>. For documentation and package installation, visit <https://tspoto.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed solution that constructs prototypes and enrich them with context aggregation to serve as higher-level concepts used in a glassbox surrogate model. The input to the approach are raw dataset and blackbox classifier. The final output is a surrogate model that explains decision of the blackbox model with interpretable components.

2. Related works

Research on Explainable AI (XAI) has gained significant momentum over the past decade, leading to the development of numerous algorithms that offer insight into the decision-making processes of black-box models. These insights vary in form, depth, and the types of questions they address, shedding light on different aspects of an AI model's operations at various levels of detail.

In the following sections, we briefly outline the landscape of XAI research, position our work within this field, and define the primary challenges in developing XAI methods for time series classification.

2.1. Spectrum of explainable AI methods

XAI algorithms can be classified on multiple levels. In this section, we loosely follow the classification outlined by [3], addressing aspects such as granularity, applicability, internal structure, and the types of explanations generated.

In terms of explanation granularity, the XAI algorithms can be divided into two categories: 1) local explanations, which concentrate on generating explanations for specific instances, and 2) global explanations, which aim to provide overall explanations for the entire model. Local explanations are exemplified by widely known methods such as SHAP [4] or LIME [5]. On the other hand, global explanations rely primarily on established statistical techniques such as partial dependence plots, accumulated local effects, functional decomposition, importance of permutation features, or prototype discovery [6].

Regarding the applicability of explanations, a distinction can be made between model-agnostic algorithms, which can be applied regardless of the specific model, and model-specific methods, which are tailored to work with a particular type of model.

Model-agnostic methods treat the model being explained as a black-box, making no assumptions about its internal mechanisms. This characteristic provides robustness, enabling these methods to be applied to various types of systems that transform a predetermined set of inputs into outputs. Some examples of model-agnostic methods include SHAP, LIME, Anchor [7], LORE [8], EXPLAN [9], as well as most global explainers [10].

Conversely, model-specific methods leverage certain properties of the algorithm they explain, which can enhance their performance. In some cases, a model-agnostic method can be adapted or redesigned to become model-specific. For instance, the SHAP method has both a model-agnostic version called KernelSHAP [11] and model-specific versions such as TreeSHAP [12] or DeepSHAP [4]. These model-specific variations are designed to provide faster explanations for different families of machine learning algorithms.

This classification can be further divided into inherently interpretable models and post hoc explainers. The first group consists of AI systems designed to be interpretable, allowing their decisions to be explained by tracking the process used to make them. Commonly used methods within this group include linear regression and decision trees. The trend of favoring efficient glass-box, inherently interpretable models over post hoc approaches is gaining popularity. This was initially addressed in [13], where the author stated that there is no scientifically proven dependency between model complexity and efficiency. A similar approach was presented in [14], introducing explainable boosting machines, an interpretable and efficient method.

On the other hand, post hoc explainers assume that explanations can be generated without interfering with the internal mechanics of the model being explained. However, the existence of post hoc and inherently interpretable models in the same explanation mechanism is not mutually exclusive. In fact, many post hoc explainers, such as the previously mentioned model-agnostic explainers, use inherently interpretable models that locally mimic the behavior of the original model.

The trend of employing inherently interpretable models has also been embraced in the realm of Deep Neural Networks, leading to the development of architectures capable of extracting prototypes from the original input and using them as explanations for the decision-making process [15]. Pioneering architectures utilizing this concept include ProtoPNet [16], TesNet [17], ProtoPool [18], ProtoPShare [19], and others. This approach involves training prototypes, which are specific parts of the original inputs deemed important for classifying a particular instance. These prototypes lie at the intersection of several types of explanations mentioned earlier in this section. On one hand, they provide local explanations by focusing on explaining predictions for individual instances. On the other hand, a set of prototypes for all instances in one class can be considered a global explanation for that class. Furthermore, they can be considered example-based explanations, as the prototypes are derived from original inputs in the training set. Finally, they are model-specific methods, as the prototype layer is inherently tied to the architecture of a neural network.

Concerning the form of explanations, four leading strategies can be distinguished: 1) feature importance attribution methods, 2) counterfactual and contrastive explanations, 3) rule-based explanations and 4) visual explanations.

In the first group, prominent algorithms like SHAP, LIME, and BreakDown [20] take the lead. Despite their different underlying mechanisms, they all provide local explanations in the form of feature importances and feature impacts. These explanations can shed light on how

different features influence the model’s decision for a particular instance. Although seemingly straightforward, this form of explanation is among the most popular, but it is also prone to serious interpretation errors. Numerous recent works from data-science perspectives [21, 22] and various fields, including industry [23] and healthcare [24], have pointed out the illusory simplicity and pitfalls of such explanations.

The group of counterfactual and contrastive explanations includes approaches like [25]. These explanations aim to provide information on how changing the features of a given instance can alter the model’s classification result. Popular counterfactual explainers include DiCE (Diverse Counterfactual Explanations) [26], which provides minimal perturbations needed to change the model’s decision for a specific instance, and Actionable Recourse in Linear Classification [27], which generates counterfactuals by only perturbing actionable variables that can be changed in reality. CARLA (Counterfactual And Recourse Library) [28] offers a framework integrating multiple counterfactual explanation methods. These methods solely focus on providing counterfactual explanations and do not offer other insights into the model decisions.

The rule-based explainers are dominated by three state-of-the-art algorithms, as mentioned earlier: Anchor, LORE, and EXPLAN. These algorithms provide explanations in the form of human-readable rules, easily interpretable even by non-data scientists. The Anchor algorithm employs a modified beam search mechanism combined with a Multi-Armed-Bandit [29] exploration mechanism to find rules describing the class of the explained instance in its local neighborhood. A comprehensive survey on rule-based explainers were given in [30, 31] The rule-based explainers are very often combined with argumentative frameworks which allows for more complex reasoning based on rules, facts and arguments. The argument in such a framework can defend or attack other arguments and the framework is used to find a consensus and assess the validity of the conclusions that was reached. In particular, it makes it possible to the human to contest explanations provided by the explanation mechanism and interactively participate in the process of explanation. The most recent approach that incorporates this mechanism was given in [32, 33], where the authors evaluated its validity in the case of tabular datasets.

Lastly, the visual explanations aim in developing different ways of presentation of explanations in order to boost their understandability by a human. This field mostly benefits from the achievements of visual analytics methods [34, 35, 36], and human-computer and human-AI interaction approaches [37, 38, 39]. Visual explanations include saliency maps for deep neural networks [40], task-specific visualizations [41] and more general frameworks such as [42, 43]. However, most of the applications of this techniques concern images.

2.2. *Explainable AI for time series*

One of the biggest challenges in XAI for time series is that this type of data is underrepresented among XAI methods. Other modalities, such as text, images, and tabular data, are well-studied and have numerous methods across all classes of XAI algorithms described earlier in this section. A comprehensive survey on explainability mechanisms for time series can be found in [44].

The most common types of XAI algorithms applied to time series are based on feature-attribution schemes combined with simple visualizations. This includes saliency maps, the SHAP explainer with a dedicated implementation for deep neural networks, and a wide range of Grad-CAM variations. For instance, in [45], the authors propose the dCAM method, designed for CNN-based architectures, which provides explanations in the form of activation maps for multivariate time series. In [46], the authors propose an interpretable multivariate time-series classification mechanism that highlights a time-window fragment of the time series contributing

most to the model’s class label prediction. This method treats time-series data as tabular data. In [41], the authors propose an extension of KernelSHAP, using meaningful slices of the time series as meta-features instead of point-in-time features.

An interesting approach is found in [47], where authors provide interactive visualizations of the latent-space representation of time-series embeddings. However, the main drawback of visualization methods is that they place the responsibility for analyzing results on the expert. Although these methods highlight important time series fragments, they leave the expert to interpret how these fragments are processed by the model to reach a decision.

Prototype-based explanations also exist in the time-series domain, including shapelets [48], DTW-based prototypes [49], and post-hoc prototypes discussed later in the text. Shapelet-based and DTW-based prototypes can be considered part of the preprocessing stage, thus enhancing interpretability from a data perspective, without offering insights into black-box model decisions.

These slices are defined based on similar frequencies or time-domain chunks, serving as atomic values for the perturbation mechanism. In [50], the authors introduce TapNet, an attentional prototype network, where prototypes are calculated as the mean value of sample embeddings for each class. However, these prototypes primarily serve as internal representations to enhance learning rather than providing interpretability. Similar approaches, such as those in [51, 52, 53, 54], use prototypes to support learning, with the concept rooted in Liu et al.’s original work [15].

Existing prototype-based explanations have notable limitations. Prototypes provide local explanations with some reference to a global prototype but are often not model-agnostic. Typically, they require modifications to the architecture or assumptions about the black-box model’s structure. Additionally, they do not reveal relationships between extracted prototypes, leaving analysis to the end-user.

Other explanation types, such as rule-based and counterfactual explainers, are also present in the literature on time-series data. However, these explanations often assume that time-series data can be effectively represented in tabular form, either through aggregation or by using raw values in fixed time windows. Although this approach has shown success in real-life industrial applications [55], it may oversimplify time-series data. This simplification can make it more challenging for experts to interpret explanations, as they must convert between time and tabular domains.

Another approach involves transforming time-series data into formats compatible with more interpretable machine-learning methods, such as symbolic aggregation [56] (SAX). For instance, SAX has been used in [57, 58] to create interpretable, high-level features from raw data and then select relevant features for each representation, achieving a balance between performance and interpretability. However, SAX-based approaches cannot be considered true explanations for black-box models, as their aggregation phase is model-independent and does not clarify model-specific decision-making. Rule-based explanations for time-series modality have also their representatives in the field. The interesting approach was proposed in [59], where authors train simultaneously deep learning model and rule-based explainer in an online manner. The former is trained on anomaly-detection task, the latter to solve a regression model of predicting anomaly score of the detector. While the solution yield efficient solution for the problem, the produced rules were constructed from raw sensory readings, not higher-level concepts.

2.3. Problem statement

In current research and practical applications one can observe two main challenges in providing explainability for time-series classification. In Table 1 we provided a comprehensive com-

Table 1: Overview of XAI algorithms for time-series data along with their limitations. None of the existing methods simultaneously offer model-agnostic explanations while avoiding the Rashomon effect, ensuring human interpretability (rule-based), providing both local and global explanations, supporting counterfactual reasoning, and being specifically designed for time-series data. TSProto is the only approach that successfully integrates all these aspects.

Algorithm (Reference)	Type	Time-Series Readiness	Target Modality	Main Limitations
SHAP [4]	Feature attribution (local); model-agnostic with model-specific variants (DeepSHAP, TreeSHAP)	Adaptable via segmentation/time-slicing [41]	Primarily tabular/images; extendable to time series	Requires in-depth expert interpretation, low expressiveness
LIME [5]	Feature attribution (local); model-agnostic	Adaptable using windowing/segmentation	Tabular, text, images	Not originally designed for sequential data; sensitive to segmentation; requires in-depth expert interpretation
dCAM [45]	Visual explanation (activation maps); model-specific for CNNs; local	Yes	Time series	Limited to CNN-based models
XEM [46]	Visual explanation (time-window highlighting); model-specific; local	Yes	Time series	Focuses only on time-window slices; requires expert interpretation
DeepVATS [47]	Visual explanation (latent-space visualization) for DNN embeddings	Yes	Time series	Requires expert analysis of latent spaces; lacks direct feature attribution
Grad-CAM [40]	Visual explanation (saliency maps); model-specific	No	Images; extendable to time series	Low expressiveness of explanations, require expert-based analysis, only local
DiCE [26], CARLA [28]	Counterfactual explanation; model-agnostic	No	Primarily tabular	Not inherently designed for sequential data; may offer oversimplified counterfactuals
ProtoPNet [16], TesNet [17], ProtoPool [18], ProtoPShare [19]	Inherently interpretable (DNN explainer) with built-in prototype layer	No	Images	Model-specific; may be prone to Rashomon effect due to multiple valid prototypes
TapNet [50], ProSeNet [51], DPSN [52], P2ExNet [53]	Inherently interpretable (DNN explainer) with built-in prototype layer	Yes	Time-series (univariate)	Model-specific, lack of counterfactuals, lack of global explanations (except from DPSN), requires expert-based analysis, designed for univariate TS
Shapelets [48], DTW-based Prototypes [49]	Interpretable-by-design (intrinsic time-series model)	Yes	Time series	Limited to shape-based interpretation; may oversimplify complex signals
Anchor [7], LORE [8], EXPLAN [9]	Rule-based (local); model-agnostic	No	Tabular, text	Sensitive to feature engineering; prone to Rashomon effect
LUX [60]	Rule-based (local and global); model-agnostic; counterfactual	No	Tabular	Requires careful tuning; may not scale well for high-dimensional signals
MR-PETS [61]	Inherently interpretable (prototype-based), post-hoc	Yes	Time series	Model-specific
XCM [62]	Inherently interpretable (DNN explainer) with built-in attention and feature attribution, post-hoc	Yes	Time series	Model-specific, requires expert-based analysis
MTEX-CNN [63]	Model-specific explainer (CNN-based) providing visual explanations, ante-hoc	Yes	Time series	Limited to CNN architectures, requires expert-based analysis

parison of most well known explainable AI algorithms that are specifically designed for time series, or commonly used in XAI community like SHAP or LIME. From this comparison several limitation stems. Firstly, in all the XAI approaches the primary focus is put on returning the fragment from an input that is important for the classifier in performing classification task. In feature importance approaches, the importance is usually a unitless value that somehow indicates the

strength of the feature or a particular value of a feature in the classifier decision calculation. In prototypical approaches, the importance is equated to the similarity of a fragment of input data to the prototypical part, which is another fragment of data from the training set. The problem with this assumption is that such an explanation is lacking context or interactions between features and prototypes, i.e. the actual explanation of how the important parts are utilized by the model is not provided. Such attempts were made for the image modality [64, 65], but time-series remain unexplored in this matter. Therefore, such an information cannot be considered a final explanation, but rather a premise which later is used by the expert to form actual explanation implicitly, based on the domain knowledge. Such simplification may very often lead to misinterpretation of explanations, as it was reported in multiple works [21, 22, 20].

Secondly, the prototypical networks and feature-importance-based methods such as SHAP, focus on local explanations only. However, there are cases, where local explanations are not enough to capture the behavior of the model. This is especially important in time-series, where data are usually analyzed in time-windows and the patterns that contribute to the decision of the model might be spread over several time-windows. For instance, a failure of an equipment or a disease of a patient may be signaled by different factors, represented as patterns in the time-series, which are not present altogether in one time-window. Using local explanations may result in the instability of explanations observed by the expert, i.e. explanations of subsequent time-windows will have different output, because of different symptoms detected. However, aggregation of these symptoms into one explanation may give the expert a broader and more detailed view of what is actually happening in the system.

Finally, in practical application, the final goal of any data mining or machine learning task is to build a model, not the explanation (although the latter is an interesting direction recently reported in [66]). Therefore, for practical reasons, it is not desired to be tightened to a particular pool of models only due to the XAI requirement, but rather to be able to apply the explanation mechanism to the selected model or models. As a consequence of that, we put a requirement of the model-agnosticism to our method.

To address the aforementioned issues we propose a rule-based, model-agnostic prototype-based explanations. The rule-based explanations are able to capture interactions and dependencies between features and prototypes. Furthermore, they are one of the most human-readable formats of explanations and can be interpreted easily even by non-data-scientists experts. To address the agnosticism of the method, we based it on SHAP explainer which is one of the most stable and theoretically grounded explainer. However, the results from SHAP are not used directly by us, as they are only used to define slices of time-series that are important for the classifier, i.e. the *explainable components*. These slices are then clustered, and based on the clusters the prototypes are defined. The prototypes are the input to the explainer that performs *context-aggregation* and produces rules that describe the behavior of the model globally.

Our work aligns with the broader research perspective outlined in the *Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) 2.0: A manifesto of open challenges and interdisciplinary research directions* [67], particularly its second and third postulates. We contribute to improving existing XAI methods by enhancing attribution techniques and refining concept-based learning adjusting it for the specific domain, i.e. time series modality in industrial applications. In the following section, we will provide detailed description of the algorithm.

Figure 2: Example of discovery of explainable components prototypes with analysis of SHAP values. It can be seen that with a usage of importance-based slices only the relevant parts of the time-series are used to form interpretable components and prototypes.

3. Post-hoc concept-based explanations

In this section we introduce a model-agnostic method that aim in creating rule-based explanations that summarizes feature importance-based explanations of any blackbox model in a concise and faithful way. In particular, we focus on methods for explaining blackbox classifiers of multidimensional time-series. We divide the process of creating an explanation into two main phases: *Explainable components and prototypes discovery* and *Context aggregation*. In the first phase the explainable components are extracted from raw data and feature-importance information, and prototypes are formed by clustering similar components. The set of prototypes forms a *context*, which is then *aggregated* into explanation. In the following section we describe this procedure in detail.

The explainable component E is a fragment of a time series that is important for the classifier in some way. In our case, it is a slice of time series obtained through mask of SHAP values as presented in Figure 2. The prototype P is a cluster of explainable components that are similar with respect to some metric. We use DTW metric because we assume that one prototype can be composed out of several explainable components of different sizes.

Context C is a set of interpretable components (and prototypes formed out of them) that interact with each other in a way that influences the decision of a model. Context aggregation is a procedure in which we filter the context to contain only the most important prototypes and discover the interactions between them. Once this step is completed, an explanation is immediately obtained.

In our case, the explanation E for model M , for instance x_i , that was trained on a dataset consisting of features $F \in \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n\}$ is considered to be of the following form given in Equation (1).

$$\Phi^{E \rightarrow M(x_i)} : C(P_1) \wedge C(P_2) \wedge \dots \wedge C(P_k) \rightarrow l \quad (1)$$

Where $C(P_i)$ is a condition that is constructed from prototypes obtained by clustering explainable components extracted from features $F_i \in F$. In the simple case, $C(P_i)$ will contain only one prototype of one feature from F , and $l \in L$ is one of the class labels used by model M .

The prototype can be additionally annotated with properties that are more understandable or desired by the user. The example of such an explanation for the case presented in Figure 2

Figure 3: The red sine wave defines a prototype barycenter. The colored sine waves represent particular explainable components forming prototype 0. The green fragment represents the most differentiable prototype from the opposite class. The grayed out sine wave is a different prototype that was discarded due to its low importance, or did not share the similarities with the prototype 0 according to clustering algorithm. The prototype 0 is additionally differentiated by the frequency property.

was given in Figure 3. It can be seen that the prototype, which is a sine wave, was additionally annotated with its frequency, and this property was used to explain the decision of the model. It is worth noting that such a result would not be possible in the case when the explainable components would be extracted based on the breakpoints from raw data. The visualization is directly generated by our method, and the color schemes used have specific meanings. The background heatmap represents the Shapley values. Green indicates fragments of the time-series that are important for the classifier but not relevant to the specific instance being explained. Red highlights the explainable components that are compared to the prototype represented by the bottom plot. Gray is used to represent fragments of the time-series considered irrelevant for the classification.

In the following section, a detailed description of explainable component discovery and context aggregation phases will be provided.

3.1. Explainable component discovery

In this work, we focus on the explanation of multidimensional time-series classification task. The dataset D is therefore represented as a three-dimensional vector or of size (M, N, K) , where M is the number of instances in dataset D , N is a length of a single sample (number of timesteps) and K denotes the number of dimensions. The single instance X_m in multidimensional time series D is defined as a two-dimensional vector of size (N, K) . One dimension k of an instance X_m will be represented as a vector $X_m^k = [x_{k,1}^m, x_{k,2}^m, \dots, x_{k,N}^m]$.

The explainable component E_k^m for a feature (dimension) k in instance m is considered a slice of time-series (i.e. subsequences of its values) that is important in some way for the blackbox model. These components are later used in a surrogate model to mimic the functionality of the black-box model. A single time series instance X_m can contain multiple explainable components for each of its K dimensions. For instance $X_m^k = [x_{k,1}^m, x_{k,2}^m, \dots, x_{k,N}^m]$, one can define $n(n+1)/2$ different subsequences. The brute-force approach to find optimal set of explainable components

would be to test all the possible combinations to see which set of explainable components gives the best results for the surrogate model. However, for obvious reasons, this is computationally infeasible. Therefore, to optimize the procedure, we propose a method that uses feature-importance attribution algorithms to detect areas of high importance and slice time-series accordingly into explainable components. We divided this method into two phases.

During the first phase for each time point $x_{k,n}^m$ in each dimension k in each time-series sample X_m its importance is calculated and stored in $s_{k,n}^m$. This results in creating an explainer domain dataset D^S that is a three-dimensional vector of exactly the same sizes as the original dataset D , where each instance $S_m^k = [s_{k,1}^m, s_{k,2}^m, \dots, s_{k,N}^m]$ contain importance for each single element in D . The importance can be calculated with any feature-importance attribution-based explainer, such as SHAP or LIME.

In the second phase, the breakpoints that define the boundaries of the explainable components are searched in the explainer domain D^S . This is based on the assumption that the explainable component is defined by the region of similar importance in S_m^k . To define these breakpoints we use the Pelt algorithm [68] with kernel-changepoint detection [69] which analyzes the statistical properties of a series and finds breakpoints that divide slices of different statistical properties. We investigated other algorithms, including binary segmentation [70], bottom-up segmentation [71], and window-based change-point similar to ADWIN [72]. However, we chose to use Pelt because the other algorithms required a fixed parameter to indicate the number of change points, whereas Pelt allows the number of change points to be adjusted based on the penalty value. This flexibility was crucial, as different instances and dimensions within the same dataset may have varying numbers of explainable components, making a fixed number of change points a suboptimal solution.

As a result, of changepoint detection phase, we obtain a set of explainable components for each feature with importances assigned to each of the component. Therefore, if breakpoints were discovered in timesteps t_1 and t_2 for instance $X_m^k = [x_{k,1}^m, x_{k,2}^m, \dots, x_{k,N}^m]$, the resulting explainable components associated with this instance will form a set of three subsequences of X_m^k defined as follows:

$$E_m^k = \begin{cases} x_{k,1}^m, \dots, x_{k,t_1}^m, \\ x_{k,t_1+1}^m, \dots, x_{k,t_2}^m, \\ x_{k,t_2+1}^m, \dots, x_{k,N}^m \end{cases}$$

With each of the explainable components of E one can associate the corresponding vector of importances from S as depicted in Figure 2. The S can be therefore used to discard components which are not important for the model, therefore should not contribute to the creation of prototypes. Once the explainable components are defined and filtered by their importance, they are clustered in order to distinguish important concepts that take part in the classification process, i.e. prototypes as shown in Figure 5. These concepts are based on the notion of a time series shape as we use for clustering a DTW-based algorithms [73] (i.e. KMeans with DTW metric). We have tested several other approaches, which are implemented and available in the software package we provide. In particular, we have tested different combinations of KMeans (with DTW and purely on Euclidean distance), KShape [74], ROCKET-based clustering [75] and Shapelet-based clustering [76]. We analyzed over 33000 parameter configurations during the grid-search optimization and found that DTW clustering was one of the most efficient, stable, and reliable methods we used, as shown in Figure 4. Unfortunately, it was also the most computationally expensive. Since we were primarily focused on F1 optimization, we chose DTW. However, it

Figure 4: Summary of a grid-search optimization across over 33000 models. The upper-left plot shows the average drop in F1 score compared to the best-achieved F1 for a particular dataset. Similarly, the upper-right plot displays the standard deviation of the F1 drop. The lower-left plot represents the number of successful trainings, while the lower-right plot illustrates the execution times for training and inference. The best results are highlighted with red boxes.

is worth noting that, in some cases or when time constraints are a factor, the ROCKET-based clustering might be an optimal choice².

Having the explainable components discovered and grouped into prototypes with time-series clustering algorithm, the second phase begins, the goal of which is *context aggregation* and the generation of explanations.

3.2. Context aggregation

The goal of context aggregation is to define which prototypes are present in which time series and what their distinctive features are that will allow us to construct explanation rules. To achieve this, we perform two-step aggregation. First, we define which prototypes are present in each of the samples and aggregate their properties to more semantic descriptions (i.e., concepts), as shown in Figure 6. In the practical implementation of our method we included descriptions of the prototypes presented in Table 2. However, the set of desired prototype characteristics is not

²All the algorithms are implemented in our Python package.

Figure 5: Each sample from dataset is first sliced into explainable components. Then similar explainable components are clustered separately for each dimension. Unimportant components are discarded. After that, each explainable component within each cluster is additionally enriched with additional description (frequency in this case).

limited by the method, and custom characteristics can be designed additionally if they are more desired by the addressees of the explanations. After that, we construct a rule-based model, which is considered an explanation of the blackbox model.

We use the prototypes as a visual form of explanation, which provides a general concept to the user, which later is enriched with more descriptive properties such as duration, frequency, and other statistical measures that are acceptable by the user. In other words, this helps to add two layers of information to the surrogate classifier which altogether form a context. First layer is associated with a shape of explainable component (similar shapes form same prototype/cluster) and is a visual component of the final explanations. The second layer allows us to differentiate between semantically different, yet visually similar shapes (for instance, sine wave of different frequencies). The first layer allows us to include a general concept description that is present in the time series and is important for the model in the classification process. The second layer allows us to understand what property of this concept is important in differentiating the different classes.

The explanation itself is built in a straightforward way. The tabular representation of time-series is passed to a decision tree classifier algorithm that constructs a classification tree. These two layers are combined in a form of visual, rule-based explanation as presented on the right side of the Figure 6.

In the following section, we present in-depth comparison of a performance of our explanation method on various univariate and multivariate time series classification tasks, as well as a case study on real-life dataset.

4. Evaluation

In this section, we present an evaluation of our approach both from the quantitative and qualitative perspectives. In case of the quantitative evaluation, we performed a comprehensive comparison with several state-of-the-art algorithms in terms of fidelity with black-box models. We selected only the algorithms that are based on prototypes (such as MR-PETSC), or are inherently interpretable (i.e. decision trees).

Table 2: Existing prototype descriptions in current implementation of the method.

Stat Function Name	Description
Maximum	Maximum value of the time series segment that is assigned to particular prototype (belonging to the same cluster as prototype)
Minimum	Minimum value of the time series segment that is assigned to particular prototype
Standard Deviation	Measures the spread of values around the mean within the data segment assigned as being the part of prototype
Mean	Average value within the time series segment that is assigned to particular prototype
Trend	Represents the trend within the prototype, calculated as the average trend of all the segments forming the prototype
Duration	Number of non-NaN entries within the prototype (data length of a segment)
Frequency	Dominant frequency of the data in the prototype. This is estimated with Fourier transform.
Number of Occurrence	Indicates number occurrence of a prototype within the analyzed time series (i.e. number of time-series slices that are assigned to the same cluster as a given prototype)
Similarity	Measures similarity between data segments and prototypes
Startpoint	First index where the time-series where the particular prototype appears

Figure 6: Each multidimensional sample is aggregated into tabular representation in a way that presence of each prototype in a given sample is one-hot encoded and additional statistical properties are added as second layer description of the prototype.

Figure 7: The architecture we used for the evaluation on all benchmark tasks. The size of the LSTM Convolutional layer and last Dense layer may vary depending on the size of the input, but the overall structure is shared between datasets.

For the qualitative comparison, we provided a real-life scenario that involved a problem of explainable failure detection in Metro de Porto dataset [77]. In this scenario we have built a custom anomaly-detector and generate explanations for detected anomalies. And based on the expert comments on the nature of the failures obtained from [77], we evaluated the correctness of the explanations.

The results of both experiments are discussed in detail in the following sections.

4.1. Quantitative evaluation

In industrial settings, time-series data is the predominant modality for monitoring and analyzing processes, making it a natural choice for evaluating methods designed for Industry 4.0 applications. However, due to the diversity of industrial environments, datasets from different domains can vary significantly in structure, scale, and complexity. Despite these differences, they share key characteristics, including the temporal nature of the data and the need for expert-driven analysis. Given these commonalities, the UCR Time Series Classification Archive serves as a valuable benchmark for evaluating our proposed methods. Its extensive collection of diverse time-series datasets enables rigorous assessment across various scenarios, ensuring that the methods developed are robust and applicable to a wide range of industrial contexts.

For data preprocessing, we performed only normalization on input features. As a blackbox classifier we used DNN model of the architecture presented in Figure 7 and train it with default parameters on training set consisting of 80% of the instances that were available. We retained only the datasets where the results obtained with our DNN were close to the state-of-the-art results reported in the literature and discarded the remaining datasets. The data characteristics are presented in Table 3.

For such a set of datasets we build explanations with different models including prototypical DNN architectures, and inherently explainable models based on feature-engineering approach. We focused on methods that were designed to work with both univariate and multivariate time-series. The explanation models were trained on the train set and evaluated on test set. As a metric of comparison between explanation mechanism, we used the F1 score.

We performed two types of quantitative evaluation tasks. The first task was designed to check if the explanation mechanism provides explanations that are consistent with blackbox model predictions. This metrics is often denoted as fidelity or faithfulness and ensures that the explanations are correct in terms of the prediction accuracy. In this scenario, we were comparing explainers that are fully interpretable, i.e. Decision trees, Shapelets and our method. The decision tree method was trained on the same set of descriptors as TSProto (See Table 2), but it was calculated on the whole time-series, not for the time series slices within a particular prototype/concept.

The results of this task are presented in Table 4. It can be seen that our methods outperform each other in terms of the fidelity obtained on the benchmark datasets. We additionally performed the statistical tests to check the significance of the difference in performance. From the Friedman test, we obtained statistics equal to 27.02, with p-value equal to 0.00. This allowed us to reject

Dataset name	No of instances	Window Length	Dimensions	No classes
Symbols	1020	398	1	6
GunPointMaleVersusFemale	451	150	1	2
ShapesAll	1200	512	1	60
CricketY	780	300	1	12
CricketZ	780	300	1	12
OliveOil	60	570	1	4
ProximalPhalanxOutlineAgeGroup	605	80	1	3
Wine	111	234	1	2
SwedishLeaf	1125	128	1	15
Adiac	781	176	1	37
PowerCons	360	144	1	2
DodgerLoopWeekend	158	288	1	2
ECG200	200	96	1	2
Coffee	56	286	1	2
LargeKitchenAppliances	750	720	1	3
ProximalPhalanxOutlineCorrect	891	80	1	2
DodgerLoopDay	158	288	1	7
OSULeaf	442	427	1	6
BirdChicken	40	512	1	2
ShapeletSim	200	500	1	2
DiatomSizeReduction	322	345	1	4
Lighting2	121	637	1	2
ItalyPowerDemand	1096	24	1	2
DistalPhalanxOutlineCorrect	876	80	1	2
ECGFiveDays	884	136	1	2
CricketX	780	300	1	12
UMD	180	150	1	3
MoteStrain	1272	84	1	2
Trace	200	275	1	4
BME	180	128	1	3
Herring	128	512	1	2
GunPointOldVersusYoung	451	150	1	2
SmallKitchenAppliances	750	720	1	3
SyntheticControl	600	60	1	6
DistalPhalanxTW	539	80	1	6
WormsTwoClass	258	900	1	2
GunPointAgeSpan	451	150	1	2
MiddlePhalanxOutlineAgeGroup	554	80	1	3
Beef	60	470	1	5
RefrigerationDevices	750	720	1	3
SmoothSubspace	300	15	1	3
Lighting7	143	319	1	7
WordSynonyms	905	270	1	25
ProximalPhalanxTW	605	80	1	6
MedicalImages	1141	99	1	10
ToeSegmentation2	166	343	1	2
Plane	210	144	1	7
MiddlePhalanxTW	553	80	1	6
HandMovementDirection	234	400	10	4
ERing	300	65	4	6
Cricket	180	1197	6	12
SelfRegulationSCP2	380	1152	7	2
BasicMotions	80	100	6	4
Libras	360	45	2	15
Epilepsy	275	206	3	4
SelfRegulationSCP1	561	896	6	2
AtrialFibrillation	30	640	2	3
RacketSports	303	30	6	4
UWaveGestureLibrary	440	315	3	8
ArticulatoryWordRecognition	575	144	9	25
Handwriting	1000	152	3	26

Table 3: Description of datasets used in evaluation

the null hypothesis. With 4 algorithms and 61 datasets, we had 3 x 180 degrees of freedom, respectively. This allowed us to determine that the critical value for $F(3, 180)$ for $\alpha = 0.05$ is 0.60, which proves the TSProto the highest average score is statistically significant. The critical distance along with average ranking values is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Critical distance for the fidelity test presented in Table 4.

Figure 9: The example of one of the explanations for the ECG200 dataset from UCR repository.

The example of a TSProto model for one of the benchmark cases is presented in Figure 9. The dataset represents the ECG200 dataset that contain ECG signals of healthy and sick people. There are three subpatterns visible in the dataset as reported in [78], located at the beginning, in the middle and at the end of the time series samples. It can be observed that the characteristic parts of these patterns were correctly marked by TSProto and used in building a decision tree.

The second task was designed to evaluate the quality of the prototypes that we extracted with our method and the enrichment added during the context aggregation phase compared to other interpretable methods such as MR-PETSC, and others. In the aforementioned methods the prototypes are usually passed through the dense layer, or nonlinear classifier layers to obtain final classification. While our method is fully interpretable, we enhanced it by passing our prototypes and their descriptions through a nonlinear extreme boosting classifier to achieve the final classification. This allowed us to create a comparable architecture that can be evaluated alongside other solutions built on similar paradigms. The results of this task are presented in Table 5. It can also be observed that the prototypes and their descriptions generated with TSProto gives the highest quality predictions. From the Friedman test, we obtained statistics equal to 61.47, with p-value equal to 0.00. With 5 algorithms and 61 datasets, we had 4 x 240 degrees of freedom, respectively. This allowed us to determine that the critical value for $F(4, 240)$ for $\alpha = 0.05$ is

Dataset name	TSPROTO	Decision Tree	Shapelets
Adiac	0.45 ± 0.03	0.33 ± 0.02	0.00 ± 0.00
ArticularyWordRecognition	0.36 ± 0.01	0.11 ± 0.01	0.74 ± 0.06
AtrialFibrillation	0.00 ± 0.00	0.22 ± 0.09	0.16 ± 0.09
BME	0.95 ± 0.05	0.76 ± 0.09	0.74 ± 0.09
BasicMotions	0.97 ± 0.05	0.98 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.06
Beef	0.68 ± 0.13	0.45 ± 0.12	0.43 ± 0.14
BirdChicken	0.74 ± 0.14	0.58 ± 0.16	0.66 ± 0.14
Coffee	0.76 ± 0.16	0.64 ± 0.14	0.79 ± 0.13
Cricket	0.72 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.02	0.76 ± 0.06
CricketX	0.41 ± 0.04	0.33 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.03
CricketY	0.45 ± 0.04	0.31 ± 0.03	0.22 ± 0.04
CricketZ	0.48 ± 0.02	0.37 ± 0.03	0.34 ± 0.06
DiatomSizeReduction	0.98 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.02	0.88 ± 0.11
DistalPhalanxOutlineCorrect	0.89 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.01	0.83 ± 0.03
DistalPhalanxTW	0.56 ± 0.06	0.49 ± 0.04	0.44 ± 0.10
DodgerLoopDay	0.51 ± 0.09	0.43 ± 0.08	0.22 ± 0.14
DodgerLoopWeekend	0.99 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.05	0.89 ± 0.10
ECG200	0.90 ± 0.04	0.71 ± 0.04	0.81 ± 0.05
ECGFiveDays	0.93 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.05
ERing	0.90 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.10
Epilepsy	0.86 ± 0.03	0.81 ± 0.02	0.75 ± 0.07
GunPointAgeSpan	0.97 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.05
GunPointMaleVersusFemale	0.92 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.01	0.83 ± 0.11
GunPointOldVersusYoung	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	0.68 ± 0.08
HandMovementDirection	0.27 ± 0.00	0.15 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.06
Handwriting	0.12 ± 0.00	0.04 ± 0.01	0.14 ± 0.02
Herring	0.57 ± 0.16	0.66 ± 0.10	0.57 ± 0.10
ItalyPowerDemand	0.98 ± 0.01	0.76 ± 0.03	0.83 ± 0.08
LargeKitchenAppliances	0.80 ± 0.07	0.60 ± 0.03	0.57 ± 0.06
Libras	0.52 ± 0.00	0.39 ± 0.02	0.42 ± 0.05
Lighting2	0.59 ± 0.09	0.67 ± 0.08	0.60 ± 0.08
Lighting7	0.64 ± 0.11	0.59 ± 0.06	0.58 ± 0.12
MedicalImages	0.71 ± 0.03	0.53 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.06
MiddlePhalanxOutlineAgeGroup	0.86 ± 0.03	0.84 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.02
MiddlePhalanxTW	0.66 ± 0.08	0.50 ± 0.04	0.62 ± 0.06
MoteStrain	0.89 ± 0.01	0.85 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.03
OSULeaf	0.47 ± 0.04	0.44 ± 0.04	0.32 ± 0.06
OliveOil	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00
Plane	0.94 ± 0.03	0.81 ± 0.05	0.92 ± 0.02
PowerCons	0.99 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.02	0.76 ± 0.09
ProximalPhalanxOutlineAgeGroup	0.83 ± 0.14	0.79 ± 0.03	0.82 ± 0.11
ProximalPhalanxOutlineCorrect	0.92 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.05
ProximalPhalanxTW	0.65 ± 0.10	0.65 ± 0.08	0.00 ± 0.00
RacketSports	0.51 ± 0.00	0.48 ± 0.02	0.52 ± 0.07
RefrigerationDevices	0.52 ± 0.06	0.55 ± 0.03	0.40 ± 0.05
SelfRegulationSCP1	0.86 ± 0.00	0.73 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.06
SelfRegulationSCP2	0.53 ± 0.07	0.49 ± 0.03	0.52 ± 0.05
ShapeletSim	0.51 ± 0.10	0.59 ± 0.05	0.57 ± 0.13
ShapesAll	0.51 ± 0.03	0.39 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.07
SmallKitchenAppliances	0.78 ± 0.03	0.61 ± 0.02	0.64 ± 0.04
SmoothSubspace	0.87 ± 0.06	0.83 ± 0.04	0.31 ± 0.08
SwedishLeaf	0.72 ± 0.01	0.41 ± 0.03	0.45 ± 0.04
Symbols	0.92 ± 0.05	0.90 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.02
SyntheticControl	0.85 ± 0.03	0.87 ± 0.02	0.76 ± 0.06
ToeSegmentation2	0.60 ± 0.08	0.80 ± 0.04	0.81 ± 0.08
Trace	0.97 ± 0.03	1.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00
UMD	0.76 ± 0.15	0.93 ± 0.05	0.58 ± 0.08
UWaveGestureLibrary	0.80 ± 0.00	0.15 ± 0.01	0.63 ± 0.11
Wine	0.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00	1.00 ± 0.00
WordSynonyms	0.21 ± 0.03	0.21 ± 0.02	0.30 ± 0.04
WormsTwoClass	0.86 ± 0.03	0.69 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.06
Total Wins	38	13	14

Table 4: Results from the fidelity evaluation

0.74. The TSPROTO obtained the highest rank among all the methods making it comparable with complex inherently interpretable methods. The critical distance along with the average ranking values is presented in Figure 10.

Dataset name	TSPProto	Shapelets	MR-PETSC	XCM	MTEX-CNN
Adiac	0.63 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.09	0.60 ± 0.03	0.29 ± 0.09	0.27 ± 0.14
ArticularyWordRecognition	0.91 ± 0.00	0.87 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.00	0.71 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.02
AtrialFibrillation	0.11 ± 0.00	0.24 ± 0.13	0.32 ± 0.04	0.24 ± 0.08	0.29 ± 0.09
BME	0.99 ± 0.01	0.79 ± 0.10	0.91 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.08
BasicMotions	1.00 ± 0.00	0.88 ± 0.09	0.95 ± 0.04	0.95 ± 0.04	0.97 ± 0.04
Beef	0.59 ± 0.17	0.41 ± 0.10	0.77 ± 0.05	0.73 ± 0.07	0.40 ± 0.27
BirdChicken	0.79 ± 0.11	0.71 ± 0.16	0.88 ± 0.05	0.85 ± 0.09	0.56 ± 0.15
Coffee	0.92 ± 0.06	0.88 ± 0.08	0.95 ± 0.04	0.89 ± 0.14	0.47 ± 0.25
Cricket	0.80 ± 0.00	0.90 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.01	0.68 ± 0.07	0.89 ± 0.05
CricketX	0.52 ± 0.05	0.69 ± 0.02	0.65 ± 0.03	0.67 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.03
CricketY	0.61 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.07	0.66 ± 0.02	0.65 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.02
CricketZ	0.71 ± 0.02	0.45 ± 0.06	0.69 ± 0.02	0.67 ± 0.02	0.37 ± 0.02
DiatomSizeReduction	0.98 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.04	0.00 ± 0.00	0.85 ± 0.15	0.90 ± 0.05
DistalPhalanxOutlineCorrect	0.81 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.03	0.70 ± 0.02	0.73 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.18
DistalPhalanxTW	0.50 ± 0.04	0.43 ± 0.07	0.46 ± 0.05	0.51 ± 0.03	0.52 ± 0.06
DodgerLoopDay	0.54 ± 0.07	0.30 ± 0.06	0.00 ± 0.00	0.56 ± 0.04	0.30 ± 0.14
DodgerLoopWeekend	0.98 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.04	0.00 ± 0.00	0.92 ± 0.05	0.97 ± 0.01
ECG200	0.85 ± 0.05	0.76 ± 0.08	0.83 ± 0.04	0.85 ± 0.03	0.84 ± 0.02
ECGFiveDays	0.98 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.06	0.93 ± 0.07	0.74 ± 0.32	0.87 ± 0.10
ERing	0.97 ± 0.00	0.85 ± 0.05	0.88 ± 0.04	0.09 ± 0.04	0.84 ± 0.05
Epilepsy	0.98 ± 0.00	0.90 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.04
GunPointAgeSpan	0.98 ± 0.01	0.92 ± 0.05	0.97 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.04	0.74 ± 0.05
GunPointMaleVersusFemale	0.97 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.12	0.99 ± 0.01	0.87 ± 0.10	0.80 ± 0.09
GunPointOldVersusYoung	1.00 ± 0.00	0.92 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.05	1.00 ± 0.00
HandMovementDirection	0.35 ± 0.00	0.29 ± 0.05	0.25 ± 0.05	0.32 ± 0.03	0.13 ± 0.02
Handwriting	0.55 ± 0.00	0.25 ± 0.07	0.37 ± 0.07	0.14 ± 0.01	0.20 ± 0.03
Herring	0.46 ± 0.07	0.53 ± 0.10	0.61 ± 0.04	0.43 ± 0.08	0.41 ± 0.07
ItalyPowerDemand	0.96 ± 0.01	0.80 ± 0.08	0.88 ± 0.03	0.82 ± 0.14	0.97 ± 0.01
LargeKitchenAppliances	0.84 ± 0.03	0.66 ± 0.06	0.89 ± 0.01	0.86 ± 0.01	0.47 ± 0.08
Libras	0.85 ± 0.00	0.51 ± 0.08	0.81 ± 0.03	0.56 ± 0.18	0.63 ± 0.31
Lighting2	0.65 ± 0.10	0.56 ± 0.13	0.77 ± 0.02	0.73 ± 0.09	0.58 ± 0.03
Lighting7	0.74 ± 0.05	0.60 ± 0.07	0.74 ± 0.06	0.73 ± 0.07	0.40 ± 0.02
MedicalImages	0.76 ± 0.03	0.29 ± 0.06	0.48 ± 0.03	0.56 ± 0.03	0.51 ± 0.22
MiddlePhalanxOutlineAgeGroup	0.61 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.05	0.43 ± 0.03	0.44 ± 0.06	0.48 ± 0.03
MiddlePhalanxTW	0.38 ± 0.03	0.37 ± 0.03	0.36 ± 0.04	0.37 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.04
MoteStrain	0.93 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.04	0.83 ± 0.08	0.86 ± 0.03	0.79 ± 0.02
OSULeaf	0.60 ± 0.03	0.36 ± 0.08	0.95 ± 0.02	0.64 ± 0.11	0.45 ± 0.02
OliveOil	0.86 ± 0.09	0.65 ± 0.09	0.94 ± 0.04	0.09 ± 0.04	0.14 ± 0.00
Plane	0.95 ± 0.04	0.94 ± 0.05	1.00 ± 0.00	0.93 ± 0.10	0.94 ± 0.04
PowerCons	0.98 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.06	0.84 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.02
ProximalPhalanxOutlineAgeGroup	0.78 ± 0.03	0.73 ± 0.04	0.69 ± 0.02	0.69 ± 0.03	0.63 ± 0.22
ProximalPhalanxOutlineCorrect	0.76 ± 0.04	0.75 ± 0.05	0.79 ± 0.01	0.48 ± 0.16	0.46 ± 0.10
ProximalPhalanxTW	0.49 ± 0.03	0.37 ± 0.09	0.47 ± 0.01	0.45 ± 0.10	0.53 ± 0.03
RacketSports	0.95 ± 0.00	0.64 ± 0.07	0.84 ± 0.02	0.66 ± 0.09	0.70 ± 0.03
RefrigerationDevices	0.65 ± 0.03	0.42 ± 0.03	0.49 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.02	0.32 ± 0.08
SelfRegulationSCP1	0.84 ± 0.00	0.80 ± 0.05	0.70 ± 0.04	0.64 ± 0.12	0.60 ± 0.23
SelfRegulationSCP2	0.56 ± 0.00	0.47 ± 0.06	0.49 ± 0.02	0.49 ± 0.08	0.33 ± 0.00
ShapeletSim	0.65 ± 0.07	0.62 ± 0.10	0.99 ± 0.01	0.75 ± 0.06	0.37 ± 0.08
ShapesAll	0.68 ± 0.03	0.24 ± 0.06	0.76 ± 0.02	0.71 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.01
SmallKitchenAppliances	0.85 ± 0.03	0.80 ± 0.03	0.82 ± 0.02	0.66 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.11
SmoothSubspace	0.92 ± 0.06	0.40 ± 0.08	0.72 ± 0.06	0.95 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.01
SwedishLeaf	0.86 ± 0.02	0.53 ± 0.06	0.87 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.02	0.78 ± 0.03
Symbols	0.97 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.79 ± 0.04
SyntheticControl	0.95 ± 0.03	0.90 ± 0.04	0.95 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.03
ToeSegmentation2	0.77 ± 0.07	0.81 ± 0.09	0.83 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.03	0.57 ± 0.06
Trace	0.88 ± 0.05	0.98 ± 0.03	1.00 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.13	0.81 ± 0.15
UMD	0.92 ± 0.04	0.54 ± 0.07	0.95 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.04	0.68 ± 0.26
UWaveGestureLibrary	0.90 ± 0.00	0.73 ± 0.08	0.89 ± 0.01	0.81 ± 0.03	0.83 ± 0.02
Wine	0.87 ± 0.07	0.75 ± 0.13	0.76 ± 0.06	0.33 ± 0.00	0.33 ± 0.00
WordSynonyms	0.30 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.05	0.36 ± 0.02	0.36 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.03
WormsTwoClass	0.67 ± 0.04	0.59 ± 0.11	0.74 ± 0.02	0.65 ± 0.03	0.51 ± 0.12
Total Wins	27	2	22	5	5

Table 5: Results from the prototype quality evaluation.

Figure 10: Critical distance for the quality of prototypes test presented in Table 5.

Figure 11: Architecture of the network designed to learn to detect anomalies. All the activation functions were ReLU, except for the last Dense layer, where activation function which was set to softmax.

4.2. Qualitative evaluation

For the qualitative evaluation, we employ MetroPT (version 2) dataset [77]. The dataset was collected in collaboration with Porto’s urban metro public transportation service in Portugal in 2022. It contains measurements from the air compressor unit that plays important role in opening and closing metro train doors. The data includes various analog sensor readings—such as pressure, temperature, and current consumption—as well as digital control and discrete signals, alongside GPS data (latitude, longitude, and speed). Designed to support the evaluation of online machine learning models, this dataset offers valuable features and serves as a robust benchmark for predictive maintenance applications.

Our goal was to build a model that detects the anomalies and report failure if the number of anomalies exceeds some predefined threshold over a short period of time. Then, we wanted to obtain explanations on why the model decided that there was a failure detected. We used the architecture presented in Figure 11. Its training was divided into two parts: auto-encoder training and classifier training. The autoencoder was trained on the healthy data from the train set. It was used for the purpose of anomaly detection in a classical way, i.e. the large reconstruction error indicates data that differ from the healthy training data, i.e. indicating failure. The anomaly reported by the autoencoder is considered an alert.

For the failure detection, we performed well known 3-sigma approach. We calculated rolling window mean of such alerts, and mark the time series slices as failures if the rolling average of alerts was larger than 3 standard deviation away from the mean. Such data were then used to train the classifier, whose head was constructed from the autoencoder and the decoder part

was replaced by the dense layers. We kept the autoencoder part trainable, to allow the classifier perform fine-tuning. This classifier was the final input for our TSProto method, which generated explanations for the model decisions with the F1 score at the level of 0.85.

In the expert-based analysis of the MetroPT data, there were three failures within the time period we were analyzing: two failures related to air leak and one failure related to oil leak. We managed to correctly identify all of them. Our model spotted four false alarms over the monitored period.

In Figure 12 we present the failures that we detected (cyan line) over the real failures marked by the expert (red background). The blue plot shows the reconstruction error obtained from our method.

The explanations we obtained from our method were aligned with the expert knowledge about the root causes of the failures as reported in [77], which link TP3 sensor and oil temperature with the failure. We present the explanation for the last failure alert in Figure 13. For the sake of visualization purposes we included only two levels of the tree. The expert has a possibility of selecting a set of features which will be used to create concepts, hence testing different alternatives of explanations, finally choosing the one that best fits the particular problem, or use all the alternatives to get more insight into the problem. Furthermore, the expert can choose to display the contrastive sample of time series (the middle plot in a node of a decision tree) that explains the model by showing the healthy sample which shares the same concept as the faulty sample but was classified differently. The oil leak failure can be recognized by the strange behavior of the air system and variations in oil temperature, which was also detected by the explanation mechanism by detecting increased standard deviation of compressor refilling air tank (TP3 sensor). It can be observed that TSProto used whole sample as an explainable component and enriched it with statistical context.

4.3. User evaluation

The user evaluation study involved 17 participants with diverse backgrounds in explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) and Industry 4.0, ensuring that all had prior experience with XAI through research or practical applications and a solid foundation in data science. The participants were recruited from different leading research teams in Europe and companies from the Industry 4.0 area.

The objective of the study was to assess the quality of the explanations provided by TSProto in comparison to other established methods known to the participants. To achieve this, the evaluation was conducted using three different use cases: a synthetic example designed to introduce the underlying concept of TSProto, the UCR ECG200 dataset from the healthcare domain, and an anomaly detection case from Metro de Porto. The survey was conducted on an anonymous and voluntary basis, and all participants were informed of these conditions prior to their participation.

Participants first familiarized themselves with TSProto and its outputs across these cases, after which they responded to a series of questions—primarily single or multiple-choice items—with four open-ended questions that invited them to evaluate TSProto in their own words³.

Participants were then asked to answer two questions regarding their background in data science, Industry 4.0, and explainable artificial intelligence.

Following the background-related questions, they were presented with eleven questions assessing the comprehensibility, expressiveness, and overall quality of TSProto compared to other

³The full survey is accessible at <https://forms.office.com/e/cm0zKcFGSR>.

Figure 12: Results from the failure detection algorithm. The red background represents true failure, while cyan dotted line the failure detected with our approach.

Figure 13: TSPROTO explanation for the correctly detected failure of oil leak on 2022-05-31 that was observed in irregularities in Oil temperature and TP3 sensor readings. The failure is marked as class 1.

Figure 14: Distribution of participants' expertise across various related fields

methods they were familiar with or had used in practice. Among these eleven questions, four were open-ended, allowing participants to provide longer, free-text responses on the advantages and disadvantage of TSProto. The final question aimed to summarize the perspective through which TSProto was analyzed, assessing whether it was viewed from an industrial standpoint or a more general perspective.

From the analysis of the results⁴, we identified that majority of participants have background in Industry 4.0, as depicted in Figure 14. Only 11% of them declared no experience at all in this field. Majority of respondents were familiar with feature attribution methods such as LIME, or SHAP, while only around 10% of them known also the prototypical approaches such as Shapelets, ProtoPNet, etc.

The majority of the respondents declared comprehensibility of TSProto as comparable to other methods, with a slight shift towards, *More expressive*, as shown in Figure 15. Similarly in case of the comprehensibility, however here, there was a visible shift towards evaluating TSProto as very easy to understand (12%) or Somewhat easy to understand (53%). The visualization aspect of TSProto was evaluated as helpful, with no vote lower than *Moderately helpful*. The decision tree format, was also evaluated as Extremely or Very helpful, however, here some voices were strongly against it (one of participants decided it is not helpful at all in improving clarity of explanations. Both time-slices in tree nodes for factual and contrastive explanations were rated as Significantly or Somewhat improves comprehensibility and the overall quality was above the average in favour for TSProto.

The analysis of the open-ended questions revealed that the most frequently mentioned strength of TSProto was its use of time slices as explainable components, in contrast to the single-point explanations typically found in rule-based explainers, along with the visual clarity of the explanations. The most common weaknesses included difficulties in understanding technical aspects, unclear or insufficient documentation, and challenges in interpreting the decision trees without

⁴The full results from the survey are provided as supplementary materials.

Figure 15: Distribution of participants’ ratings across different features of TSPProto. The higher, the better.

proper descriptions of their components reported mostly by participants with less advanced background in XAI. Participants with a more advanced background in XAI and data science reported that, although the method provides understandable and clear explanations, the value of these explanations should be assessed based on how they are constructed. Without this knowledge, it is impossible to evaluate their quality, as they remain plots lacking context. All the aforementioned findings align with our previous research on the comprehensibility of XAI algorithms [1], which showed that for novice and intermediate participants, the explanation is often not comprehensible, while experts tend to challenge it based on their knowledge when the model or explanation conflicts with their understanding.

We followed that lead and conducted statistical analyses to determine whether there are any significant differences between the ratings obtained from these two groups. We classified participants as experts if they self-identified as *Advanced* or *Expert* on the initial survey question, with all other participants labeled as non-experts. To analyze the differences between the groups, we used the Mann-Whitney U test [79], which is appropriate for comparing two independent groups when the data is non-parametric. This test was chosen because the ratings were ordinal, meaning they represent categories with a meaningful order but not necessarily a consistent scale between them. The results of the obtained p-values are presented in the Figure 16.

Surprisingly, results suggest that there is no statistically significant difference between how experts and non-experts rate the algorithms across all tested fields. In every expertise domain, for each rating aspect, the p-values are well above the 0.05 threshold. This consistency implies that both groups perceive the algorithms similarly, which could indicate that the algorithms are robust and transparent enough to be understood and appreciated regardless of the evaluator’s expertise. It may also suggest that the evaluation criteria capture aspects of performance that do not heavily depend on specialized knowledge, or that both groups share a common standard when judging them.

5. Discussion

In the following sections, we elaborate more thoroughly on the relation of the TSPProto with respect to already existing methods for prototype-based explanations for time-series, both inherently interpretable as well as model agnostic.

Figure 16: Heatmap showing the p-values from the Mann-Whitney U test comparing the ratings of experts and non-experts across different fields and evaluation criteria. Values close to 1 indicate no significant difference between groups, while values below 0.05 would suggest a statistically significant difference.

Following that, we perform sensitivity analysis of the hyperparameters of TSPProto on the fidelity of explanations and the interpretability (defined as depth of the TSPProto decision tree).

5.1. Relation of TSPProto to other methods

The evaluation results indicate that the quality of explanations generated by our method surpasses other glass-box explanation approaches designed for time-series data, as well as specialized deep prototype networks. This has several implications, highlighting the multidimensional contributions of our work.

TSPProto introduces a model-agnostic, SHAP-compliant post-hoc method that enhances prototype-based explanations. This approach can be combined with rule-based explainers, argumentation frameworks, or inherently interpretable models, providing comprehensive insights into black-box model decisions. Importantly, our method is not intended to compete with prototype-based architectures but rather complements them by aggregating their outputs and presenting results concisely to the user. Prototypical deep neural networks (such as ProtoPNet) and TSPProto represent two fundamentally different approaches to explainability. Prototypical networks are inherently interpretable models that integrate prototypes directly within a CNN architecture by extracting them from intermediate layers and transforming them for use in dense layers during prediction. In contrast, TSPProto is a model-agnostic, post hoc explainer that imposes no architectural constraints; it leverages SHAP-based analysis to identify prototypical regions in the input space and employs clustering algorithms to aggregate these into higher-level prototypes. While ProtoPNet-like approaches explain decisions by comparing inputs to learned prototypes embedded in the model, TSPProto offers explanations by analyzing feature attributions and grouping similar patterns independently of the underlying model architecture.

Furthermore, TSPProto can integrate model-specific and prototypical techniques that outperform SHAP, leveraging them to identify interpretable components. The complementarity between prototypical approaches, such as ProtoPNet and its successors, and TSPProto lies in how prototypes are constructed and utilized in both methods. Prototypical deep neural networks generate prototypes, which are then passed through a dense layer to produce the final decision. In

TSPProto, we replace this dense layer with a fully interpretable decision tree structure, optimized so that nodes do not refer to single values but rather to time-series segments—prototypes. In our approach, these segments are generated using SHAP and DTW clustering, while in prototypical networks, they are derived through architecture-specific pooling and casting from the embedding space onto dataset patches. However, the design of TSPProto enables replacing the SHAP and DTW phases with deep prototype generation, thereby substituting the dense layers in ProtoPNet-based methods with our decision-tree structure.

Another dimension of the contribution is that our method aligns with Symbolic Aggregate approXimation (SAX) methodologies. It extracts symbolic representations from time-varying data chunks through explainable algorithms, with symbols reflecting varying levels of importance. Similar to shapelet methods, prototype-based approaches aim to identify representative subsequences that distinguish between classes. However, our results show that a pure shapelet approach yields inferior performance compared to TSPProto, which effectively filters out noisy time-series segments that could undermine shapelet transformations. This advantage is especially evident on challenging datasets like Adiac, where our method achieves results 43% better than the shapelet transformation. While TSPProto may resemble the shapelet approach in detecting interpretable components, the key difference lies in how prototype candidates are selected. In shapelets, candidates are chosen purely by analyzing raw data, identifying fragments that best differentiate time-series instances between classes. This approach makes the method susceptible to the Rashomon effect if the selected shapelets do not align with the black-box model’s decision-making process. In contrast, TSPProto selects candidates based on SHAP values, ensuring that each candidate represents a data slice that is important for the black-box model. This makes TSPProto more likely to capture and utilize the same critical patterns as the black-box model, enhancing its explainability. However, as with TSPProto, both methods can be combined. In fact, one possible approach for selecting interpretable components in our method is shapelet-based clustering, as discussed in Section 3.1, where shapelets are constructed from candidates previously identified through SHAP-based slicing.

Our approach is designed to support more interactive explanations in the future, allowing domain experts to refine prototypes generated from data, with the process iteratively repeated. Initial prototypes can also be provided by domain experts in a coarse form (e.g., sketches or segments of similar time-series) to serve as starting points, which our method can build upon to develop refined prototypes. This iterative refinement represents a promising direction in the field of explainable AI (XAI), recognized as a significant research challenge by both community members and external researchers. However, such an extension requires in-depth user studies to assess the comprehensibility of XAI algorithms, particularly in the context of time-series data. In this work, we motivated the use of rule-based explanations, drawing on our previous study [1, 80] and other related studies in the literature [81], where rule-based explainability proved to be one of the most accessible forms of communication with users. Despite the clear potential, conducting thorough user studies on the comprehensibility of XAI in time-series requires careful design and large-scale investigations, which involve understanding diverse user needs, backgrounds, and contexts. This task is essential but falls beyond the scope of our more quantitatively oriented research. Future work should prioritize this aspect to further enhance the usability and acceptance of XAI systems in practical applications.

Another promising research direction is extending our method to support additional modalities beyond time-series data. While TSPProto was specifically designed for time-series analysis, its core concept can be adapted to other data types. In particular, our approach could be extended to concept-based explanations in image-based models, such as Concept Bottleneck Models [65].

Figure 17: Time allocation across the TSPProto pipeline: Shapley value calculation, training, and inference

Identifying and clustering relevant concepts, followed by replacing the dense layer with an interpretable decision tree, could function similarly for image-based models. Furthermore, our SHAP-based slicing method, which detects important fragments of time-series data, could be integrated into Transformer-based multimodal explainers, similar to those used in image-based models like Phi-3 and LLaVA [82]. This integration could enable the combination of time-series prototypes with textual descriptions, which would be particularly valuable in industrial monitoring, medical diagnostics, and financial markets—domains where specific time-series patterns are often accompanied by rich textual descriptions that indicate desired or anomalous behaviors

One limitation of our approach is its computational expense, as it relies on SHAP values, and certain clustering algorithms such as DTW, which are inherently costly to compute. From the analysis we conducted on the real dataset from Metro de Porto, the calculation of Shapley values, training and inference consume respectively 56, 40 and 4 percents of time required for total pipeline as shown in Figure 17. The Shapley value calculation is constant, while remaining times were calculated as an average from around 3000 trials. Furthermore, the effectiveness of our method is also highly dependent on the quality of these SHAP values, underscoring the need for more efficient ways to calculate feature-importance attributions.

5.2. Sensitivity analysis of TSPProto hyperparameters

An important aspect worth noting is the sensitivity of the method to different sets of hyperparameters. The analysis were conducted on the grid-search results obtained in the evaluation phase.

Since TSPProto is based on decision trees, it may be prone to overfitting. Therefore, the parameters governing decision tree growth should be selected with caution, following best practices for this type of model [83]. However, TSPProto also has its own set of parameters that can impact both the fidelity of the explanations and their interpretability (e.g., the depth of the tree). These parameters include the Cluster Scaling Factor (CSC), Slice Length Scaling Factor (SLSF), and Importance Scaling Factor (ISL).

Cluster Scaling Factor (CSC) determines the number of clusters (prototypes) generated during the explanation process. A larger CSC results in more clusters, meaning the data is divided

Figure 18: Partial dependence plot depicting effect of Cluster Scaling Factor (CSF), Slice Length Scaling Factor (SLSF), Importance Scaling Factor (ISL) on F1 drop of TSPROTO model.

into finer segments. Slice Length Scaling Factor (SLSF) controls the minimum length of an interpretable component used to form prototypes. A larger SLSF results in larger explainable components. Finally, Importance Scaling Factor (ISL) defines the threshold for the minimum importance of an interpretable component used in decision tree construction. A higher ISL results in more components being included in the final decision tree, whereas a lower ISL includes only the most important components, marking others as irrelevant (represented as gray fragments in time-series plots, e.g. in 3).

To measure the impact of these parameters on fidelity and decision tree depth, we performed a sensitivity analysis on over 24,000 samples from grid search logs used in the evaluation. Since TSPROTO was trained on different datasets with varying F1 score ranges and decision tree depths, we defined the dependent variables in the sensitivity analysis in terms of percentage increase or decrease.

Fidelity here was measured as the percentage drop in F1 score relative to the maximum achievable F1 for a given dataset. An F1 drop of 0% represents the optimal value, while the F1 drop of 100% signifies total degradation, where the F1 score drops to zero. Similarly, the depth increase was defined as the percentage increase in decision tree depth compared to the minimal depth obtained for the given dataset. The surrogate model used in sensitivity analysis was RandomForest regressor trained to predict dependant variable form grid search output.

Figure 18 illustrates the impact of hyperparameters on the F1 drop in the TSPROTO model. It can be observed that CSC and ISL have a negative effect on the F1 drop, meaning that higher values lead to a lower drop in F1. However, their effect is minimal. In contrast, SLSF has a more noticeable impact on the F1 drop. Up to a certain threshold (around 0.7), an increase in SLSF correlates with a larger F1 drop. Beyond this point, however, the drop is no longer observed. This suggests that choosing a small SLSF can lead to a greater F1 drop and lower model quality. This observation aligns with the partial dependence plot for the same set of hyperparameters but with the dependent variable defined as percentage increase in decision tree depth (see Figure 19). Similarly, CSC and ISL have minimal effects compared to SLSF, which indicates that higher SLSF values tend to produce deeper, and therefore less interpretable, decision trees.

Following the PDP analysis, we also used Sobol' Indices [84] approach to measure how much variance in the model output can be attributed to each input variable, including interactions between variables. The results were consistent with the observation of PDP plots. The visualization of the results are given in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

The SLSF dominates the sensitivity analysis, with an extremely high first-order ($S1 = 0.938$) and total-order ($ST = 1.003$). This suggests that changes in this parameter alone explain nearly

Figure 19: Partial dependence plot depicting effect of Cluster Scaling Factor (CSF), Slice Length Scaling Factor (SLSF), Importance Scaling Factor (ISL) on decision tree depth increase of TSPROTO model.

Figure 20: Sobol' sensitivity analysis of Cluster Scaling Factor (CSF), Slice Length Scaling Factor (SLSF), Importance Scaling Factor (ISL) on F1 drop of TSPROTO model.

Figure 21: Sobol' sensitivity analysis of Cluster Scaling Factor (CSF), Slice Length Scaling Factor (SLSF), Importance Scaling Factor (ISL) on decision tree depth increase of TSPROTO model.

all the variance in F1 drop. The ISF has low $S1$ (0.011) and ST (0.058), indicating that its effect is minimal and mostly due to interactions rather than direct influence. The CSF shows negligible first-order ($S1 = 0.005$) and total-order ($ST = 0.016$) contributions, reinforcing that it plays a minor role in affecting F1 drop. The strongest interaction is between SLSF and ISF ($S2 = 0.049$). This suggests that these two parameters have a joint effect on F1 drop. The interaction between CSF and SLSF ($S2 = 0.003$) is very weak, confirming that the CSF has a minimal role. Interestingly, the interaction between CSF and ISF ($S2 = -0.011$) is negative. While negative $S2$ values can be within the margin of numerical error, this might indicate opposing effects, meaning that increasing one while decreasing the other could stabilize F1 drop, which makes sense, as the number of additional clusters would be removed by the ISF responsible for filtering unimportant fragments of time series

Similar results were obtained for the depth increase. The Slice length scaling factor exhibits the highest first-order effect ($S1 = 0.673$), suggesting that it directly contributes to the variation in Depth increase more than other parameters. Its total-order index ($ST = 0.886$) further confirms that both its direct effect and interactions play a crucial role. The Importance scaling factor has a moderate total effect ($ST = 0.301$), but its first-order index ($S1 = 0.107$) is much lower, indicating that a significant portion of its impact arises from interactions with other parameters. The Cluster scaling factor has a very low first-order effect ($S1 = 0.006$) and a small total effect ($ST = 0.039$), implying that it plays a negligible role in Depth increase. The most notable interaction occurs between Slice length scaling factor and Importance scaling factor ($S2 = 0.184$), meaning that these two parameters jointly influence the depth increase significantly. The interactions between CSF and the other parameters are weak ($S2 = 0.01$), reinforcing the conclusion that CSF has little effect on depth increase.

These results suggest that Slice length scaling factor is the dominant contributor to Depth increase, both individually and through interactions. The Importance scaling factor contributes primarily through interactions, while the Cluster scaling factor has minimal influence.

The final recommendation that stem from this analysis is to focus on tuning SLSF as the primary control for both depth and F1 performance. As a second most important parameter, adjust the ISF as a secondary control, especially if further depth control or F1 stabilization is needed. Tuning CSF does not significantly affect the outcomes. However, we also observed that the average results presented here may vary significantly depending on the characteristics of the data. Therefore, in most cases, the optimization of CSF, SLSF, and ISL should be performed separately for different datasets.

6. Summary

Our work introduces TSPProto, a model-agnostic, SHAP-compliant method that enhances prototype-based explanations for time-series data, achieving superior interpretability and accuracy over existing glass-box and specialized deep prototype models. TSPProto segments important data regions into interpretable prototypes that capture symbolic representations, akin to SAX methodologies, making it adaptable to rule-based explainers and inherently interpretable models. Unlike traditional shapelet-based methods, which may struggle with complex datasets, TSPProto effectively filters out noise, delivering more accurate and interpretable results.

Analyzing raw multidimensional time-series data often requires experts to sift through intricate patterns and correlations, making it difficult to achieve clear and actionable insights. Feature-attribution approaches, while powerful, typically focus on identifying the importance

of individual inputs, which may not provide the kind of semantic clarity needed to align with human understanding. By contrast, higher-level concept-based analysis shifts the focus from raw data to more human-comprehensible abstractions, fostering a deeper, more intuitive transparency in the system.

TSPProto bridges data-driven and symbolic reasoning approaches, aligning with the goals of neuro-symbolic AI by combining the strengths of deep neural networks for complex feature extraction with rule-based models for building interpretable systems. Additionally, TSPProto is a step toward more human-centered explainable AI, as it generates and presents explanations at a level of abstraction that is accessible to end-users. A user evaluation confirmed the positive reception of TSPProto's distinctive features.

These concepts include characteristics such as minima, maxima, frequency, the existence of specific patterns, etc., making them highly interpretable and actionable. For example, in manufacturing, IoT sensors may generate time-series data on machine vibrations, temperatures, and power usage. By abstracting this raw data into concepts like "minimum vibration thresholds" or "temperature peaks," maintenance engineers can more effectively identify and address potential failures, ensuring smooth operations. Similarly, in energy management, time-series data on electricity consumption, voltage fluctuations, and equipment health can be transformed into concepts such as "peak consumption periods," "voltage drop occurrences" or "high-stress grid conditions," helping operators optimize energy distribution and prevent power disruptions. In the financial sector, time-series data from stock prices, trading volumes, and economic indicators can be distilled into concepts like "market volatility extremes", "trading volume spikes," or "risk periods," providing traders and analysts with clearer, actionable insights into market behavior.

Though computationally intensive due to its reliance on SHAP values, TSPProto's contributions align with trends in explainable AI and lay a foundation for future advancements in prototype refinement and interactive model interpretability. Future work may include the incorporation of interactive prototype suggestions and refinements, as well as efforts to enhance the speed and quality of SHAP calculations. This direction appears particularly promising in light of user evaluation assessments, which indicated that the simple presentation of results is insufficient for proper understanding. Participants noted that additional knowledge about how the explanations are constructed, what they describe, and how the concepts they use relate to the data is necessary.

To deepen our understanding of these challenges, we conducted a user-based evaluation, focusing on participants with an XAI background. Our goal was to measure the relative quality of XAI algorithms compared to other methods that participants were already familiar with. Conducting such a study poses significant challenges, particularly in ensuring that the evaluation captures meaningful insights while minimizing biases and measurement errors. Notably, we did not observe any statistical differences between participants who identified themselves as experts and those who considered themselves intermediate or novice users. However, our previous research suggests that such differences do exist and may become even more pronounced in real-world deployments of XAI systems. This is especially true when domain experts lack prior training in XAI, as visualization and interaction aspects play a crucial role in their ability to interpret and utilize explanations effectively [1].

Acknowledgements

This paper is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement number 101120406. The

paper reflects only the authors' view and the EC is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The paper is additionally funded by a grant from the Priority Research Area (DigiWorld) under the Strategic Programme Excellence Initiative at Jagiellonian University .

References

- [1] S. Bobek, P. Korycińska, M. Krakowska, M. Mozolewski, D. Rak, M. Zych, M. Wójcik, G. J. Nalepa, User-centric evaluation of explainability of ai with and for humans: a comprehensive empirical study (2024). arXiv:2410.15952.
URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.15952>
- [2] S. Müller, V. Toborek, K. Beckh, M. Jakobs, C. Bauckhage, P. Welke, An empirical evaluation of the rashomon effect in explainable machine learning, in: Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases: Research Track: European Conference, ECML PKDD 2023, Turin, Italy, September 18–22, 2023, Proceedings, Part III, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2023, p. 462–478. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-43418-1_28.
URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-43418-1_28
- [3] V. Belle, I. Papantonis, Principles and practice of explainable machine learning, *Frontiers in Big Data* 4 (2020).
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:221878773>
- [4] S. M. Lundberg, G. Erion, H. Chen, A. DeGrave, J. M. Prutkin, B. Nair, R. Katz, J. Himmelfarb, N. Bansal, S.-I. Lee, From local explanations to global understanding with explainable ai for trees, *Nature Machine Intelligence* 2 (1) (2020) 56–67. doi:10.1038/s42256-019-0138-9.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0138-9>
- [5] M. T. Ribeiro, S. Singh, C. Guestrin, “Why should i trust you?”: Explaining the predictions of any classifier, in: Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, KDD '16, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2016, p. 1135–1144. doi:10.1145/2939672.2939778.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939778>
- [6] C. Molnar, *Interpretable Machine Learning*, Lulu.com, Online, 2020.
- [7] M. T. Ribeiro, S. Singh, C. Guestrin, Anchors: high-precision model-agnostic explanations, in: Proceedings of the Thirty-Second AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Thirtieth Innovative Applications of Artificial Intelligence Conference and Eighth AAAI Symposium on Educational Advances in Artificial Intelligence, AAAI'18/IAAI'18/EAAI'18, AAAI Press, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, 2018, pp. 1527–1535.
- [8] R. Guidotti, A. Monreale, S. Ruggieri, D. Pedreschi, F. Turini, F. Giannotti, Local Rule-Based Explanations of Black Box Decision Systems, arXiv:1805.10820 [cs] (May 2018). doi:10.48550/arXiv.1805.10820.
URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1805.10820>

- [9] P. Rasouli, I. C. Yu, Explan: Explaining black-box classifiers using adaptive neighborhood generation, in: 2020 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN), IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–9.
- [10] M. T. Ribeiro, S. Singh, C. Guestrin, Model-agnostic interpretability of machine learning (2016). arXiv:1606.05386.
- [11] S. M. Lundberg, S.-I. Lee, A unified approach to interpreting model predictions, in: Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems, NIPS’17, Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA, 2017, pp. 4768–4777.
- [12] S. M. Lundberg, G. G. Erion, S.-I. Lee, Consistent individualized feature attribution for tree ensembles (2019). arXiv:1802.03888.
- [13] C. Rudin, Stop explaining black box machine learning models for high stakes decisions and use interpretable models instead, *Nature Machine Intelligence* 1 (5) (2019) 206–215. doi:10.1038/s42256-019-0048-x.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0048-x>
- [14] Y. Lou, R. Caruana, J. Gehrke, G. Hooker, Accurate intelligible models with pairwise interactions, in: Proceedings of the 19th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, KDD ’13, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2013, p. 623–631. doi:10.1145/2487575.2487579.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/2487575.2487579>
- [15] O. Li, H. Liu, C. Chen, C. Rudin, Deep learning for case-based reasoning through prototypes: A neural network that explains its predictions, *CoRR* abs/1710.04806 (2017). arXiv:1710.04806.
URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1710.04806>
- [16] C. Chen, O. Li, C. Tao, A. J. Barnett, J. Su, C. Rudin, This looks like that: Deep learning for interpretable image recognition, in: Proceedings of the 33rd International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems, Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA, 2019.
- [17] J. Wang, H. Liu, X. Wang, L. Jing, Interpretable image recognition by constructing transparent embedding space, in: 2021 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), 2021, pp. 875–884. doi:10.1109/ICCV48922.2021.00093.
- [18] D. Rymarczyk, Ł. Struski, M. Górszczak, K. Lewandowska, J. Tabor, B. Zieliński, Interpretable image classification with differentiable prototypes assignment, in: S. Avidan, G. Brostow, M. Cissé, G. M. Farinella, T. Hassner (Eds.), *Computer Vision – ECCV 2022*, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2022, pp. 351–368.
- [19] D. Rymarczyk, L. Struski, J. Tabor, B. Zieliński, Protopshare: Prototypical parts sharing for similarity discovery in interpretable image classification, in: Proceedings of the 27th ACM SIGKDD Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining, KDD ’21, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2021, p. 1420–1430. doi:10.1145/3447548.3467245.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3447548.3467245>

- [20] A. Gosiewska, P. Biecek, ibreakdown: Uncertainty of model explanations for non-additive predictive models, CoRR abs/1903.11420 (2019). arXiv:1903.11420.
URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1903.11420>
- [21] C. Molnar, G. König, J. Herbringer, T. Freiesleben, S. Dandl, C. A. Scholbeck, G. Casalicchio, M. Grosse-Wentrup, B. Bischl, General Pitfalls of Model-Agnostic Interpretation Methods for Machine Learning Models, in: A. Holzinger, R. Goebel, R. Fong, T. Moon, K.-R. Müller, W. Samek (Eds.), xxAI - Beyond Explainable AI: International Workshop, Held in Conjunction with ICML 2020, July 18, 2020, Vienna, Austria, Revised and Extended Papers, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2022, pp. 39–68. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-04083-2_4.
URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-04083-2_4
- [22] U. Ehsan, M. O. Riedl, Explainability Pitfalls: Beyond Dark Patterns in Explainable AI, arXiv:2109.12480 [cs] (Sep. 2021). doi:10.48550/arXiv.2109.12480.
URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2109.12480>
- [23] S. Verma, A. Lahiri, J. P. Dickerson, S.-I. Lee, Pitfalls of Explainable ML: An Industry Perspective, arXiv:2106.07758 [cs] (Jun. 2021). doi:10.48550/arXiv.2106.07758.
URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2106.07758>
- [24] M. Ghassemi, L. Oakden-Rayner, A. L. Beam, The false hope of current approaches to explainable artificial intelligence in health care, The Lancet Digital Health 3 (11) (2021) e745–e750. doi:10.1016/S2589-7500(21)00208-9.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2589750021002089>
- [25] I. Stepin, J. M. Alonso, A. Catala, M. Pereira-Fariña, A Survey of Contrastive and Counterfactual Explanation Generation Methods for Explainable Artificial Intelligence, IEEE Access 9 (2021) 11974–12001, conference Name: IEEE Access. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3051315.
- [26] R. K. Mothilal, A. Sharma, C. Tan, Explaining machine learning classifiers through diverse counterfactual explanations, in: Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, FAT* '20, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2020, p. 607–617. doi:10.1145/3351095.3372850.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3351095.3372850>
- [27] B. Ustun, A. Spangher, Y. Liu, Actionable recourse in linear classification, in: Proceedings of the Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, FAT* '19, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2019, p. 10–19. doi:10.1145/3287560.3287566.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287560.3287566>
- [28] M. Pawelczyk, S. Bielawski, J. van den Heuvel, T. Richter, G. Kasneci, Carla: A python library to benchmark algorithmic recourse and counterfactual explanation algorithms (2021). arXiv:2108.00783.
- [29] E. Kaufmann, S. Kalyanakrishnan, Information complexity in bandit subset selection, in: Annual Conference Computational Learning Theory, 2013.

- [30] G. Vilone, L. Longo, A quantitative evaluation of global, rule-based explanations of post-hoc, model agnostic methods, *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence* 4 (2021).
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:240425468>
- [31] G. Vilone, L. Rizzo, L. Longo, A comparative analysis of rule-based, model-agnostic methods for explainable artificial intelligence, in: *Irish Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Cognitive Science*, 2020.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:229345223>
- [32] L. Rizzo, L. Longo, An empirical evaluation of the inferential capacity of defeasible argumentation, non-monotonic fuzzy reasoning and expert systems, *Expert Systems with Applications* 147 (2020) 113220. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.113220>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0957417420300464>
- [33] G. Vilone, L. Longo, A novel human-centred evaluation approach and an argument-based method for explainable artificial intelligence, in: I. Maglogiannis, L. Iliadis, J. Macintyre, P. Cortez (Eds.), *Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2022, pp. 447–460.
- [34] D. Collaris, J. J. van Wijk, Comparative evaluation of contribution-value plots for machine learning understanding, *Journal of Visualization* 25 (1) (2022) 47–57. doi:[10.1007/s12650-021-00776-w](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12650-021-00776-w).
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12650-021-00776-w>
- [35] J. Suh, S. Ghorashi, G. Ramos, N.-C. Chen, S. Drucker, J. Verwey, P. Simard, Anchorviz: Facilitating semantic data exploration and concept discovery for interactive machine learning, *ACM Transactions on Interactive Intelligent Systems (TiiS)* 10 (1) (August 2019).
- [36] M. Britton, VINE: visualizing statistical interactions in black box models, *CoRR* abs/1904.00561 (2019). arXiv:[1904.00561](https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.00561).
URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1904.00561>
- [37] M. Chromik, A. Butz, Human-xai interaction: A review and design principles for explanation user interfaces, in: C. Ardito, R. Lanzilotti, A. Malizia, H. Petrie, A. Piccinno, G. Desolda, K. Inkpen (Eds.), *Human-Computer Interaction – INTERACT 2021*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2021, pp. 619–640.
- [38] U. Ehsan, P. Wintersberger, Q. V. Liao, M. Mara, M. Streit, S. Wachter, A. Riener, M. O. Riedl, Operationalizing human-centered perspectives in explainable ai, in: *Extended Abstracts of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, CHI EA '21*, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2021. doi:[10.1145/3411763.3441342](https://doi.org/10.1145/3411763.3441342).
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411763.3441342>
- [39] B. Abedin, C. Meske, I. Junglas, F. Rabhi, H. R. Motahari-Nezhad, Designing and Managing Human-AI Interactions, *Information Systems Frontiers* 24 (3) (2022) 691–697. doi:[10.1007/s10796-022-10313-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-022-10313-1).
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-022-10313-1>

- [40] R. R. Selvaraju, M. Cogswell, A. Das, R. Vedantam, D. Parikh, D. Batra, Grad-CAM: Visual Explanations from Deep Networks via Gradient-Based Localization, in: 2017 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), 2017, pp. 618–626, iSSN: 2380-7504. doi:10.1109/ICCV.2017.74.
- [41] F. Mujkanovic, V. Doskoc, M. Schirneck, P. Schäfer, T. Friedrich, timexplain - A framework for explaining the predictions of time series classifiers, CoRR abs/2007.07606 (2020). arXiv:2007.07606.
URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.07606>
- [42] D. Collaris, J. J. van Wijk, ExplainExplore: Visual Exploration of Machine Learning Explanations, in: 2020 IEEE Pacific Visualization Symposium (PacificVis), 2020, pp. 26–35, iSSN: 2165-8773. doi:10.1109/PacificVis48177.2020.7090.
- [43] A. Chatzimparmpas, R. M. Martins, K. Kucher, A. Kerren, Featureenvi: Visual analytics for feature engineering using stepwise selection and semi-automatic extraction approaches, IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics 28 (04) (2022) 1773–1791. doi:10.1109/TVCG.2022.3141040.
- [44] A. Theissler, F. Spinnato, U. Schlegel, R. Guidotti, Explainable ai for time series classification: A review, taxonomy and research directions, IEEE Access 10 (2022) 100700–100724. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3207765.
- [45] P. Boniol, M. Meftah, E. Remy, T. Palpanas, Dcam: Dimension-wise class activation map for explaining multivariate data series classification, in: Proceedings of the 2022 International Conference on Management of Data, SIGMOD '22, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2022, p. 1175–1189. doi:10.1145/3514221.3526183.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3514221.3526183>
- [46] K. Fauvel, E. Fromont, V. Masson, P. Faverdin, A. Termier, Xem: An explainable-by-design ensemble method for multivariate time series classification, Data Min. Knowl. Discov. 36 (3) (2022) 917–957. doi:10.1007/s10618-022-00823-6.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10618-022-00823-6>
- [47] V. Rodriguez-Fernandez, D. Montalvo, F. Piccialli, G. J. Nalepa, D. Camacho, Deepvats: Deep visual analytics for time series (2023). doi:10.48550/ARXIV.2302.03858.
URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.03858>
- [48] L. Ye, E. Keogh, Time series shapelets: A new primitive for data mining, in: Proceedings of the 15th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, KDD '09, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2009, p. 947–956. doi:10.1145/1557019.1557122.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/1557019.1557122>
- [49] X. Chang, F. Tung, G. Mori, Learning discriminative prototypes with dynamic time warping, CoRR abs/2103.09458 (2021). arXiv:2103.09458.
URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.09458>
- [50] X. Zhang, Y. Gao, J. Lin, C.-T. Lu, Tapnet: Multivariate time series classification with attentional prototypical network, in: AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, 2020.
URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:210703726>

- [51] Y. Ming, P. Xu, H. Qu, L. Ren, Interpretable and steerable sequence learning via prototypes, CoRR abs/1907.09728 (2019). arXiv:1907.09728.
URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1907.09728>
- [52] W. Tang, L. Liu, G. Long, Interpretable time-series classification on few-shot samples, CoRR abs/2006.02031 (2020). arXiv:2006.02031.
URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.02031>
- [53] D. Mercier, A. Dengel, S. Ahmed, P2exnet: Patch-based prototype explanation network, in: H. Yang, K. Pasupa, A. C.-S. Leung, J. T. Kwok, J. H. Chan, I. King (Eds.), Neural Information Processing, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2020, pp. 318–330.
- [54] S. Das, P. Xu, Z. Dai, A. Endert, L. Ren, Interpreting deep neural networks through prototype factorization, in: 2020 International Conference on Data Mining Workshops (ICDMW), 2020, pp. 448–457. doi:10.1109/ICDMW51313.2020.00068.
- [55] S. Bobek, M. Kuk, J. Brzegowski, E. Brzywczy, G. J. Nalepa, KnAC: an approach for enhancing cluster analysis with background knowledge and explanations, Applied Intelligence (Nov. 2022). doi:10.1007/s10489-022-04310-9.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10489-022-04310-9>
- [56] J. Lin, E. Keogh, L. Wei, S. Lonardi, Experiencing sax: a novel symbolic representation of time series, Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery 15 (2) (2007) 107–144.
URL <http://scholar.google.de/scholar.bib?q=info:N7PpfbwMDFgJ:scholar.google.com/&output=citation&hl=de&ct=citation&cd=0>
- [57] P. Senin, S. Malinchik, Sax-vsm: Interpretable time series classification using sax and vector space model, in: 2013 IEEE 13th International Conference on Data Mining, 2013, pp. 1175–1180. doi:10.1109/ICDM.2013.52.
- [58] T. L. Nguyen, S. Gsponer, I. Ilie, G. Ifrim, Interpretable time series classification using all-subsequence learning and symbolic representations in time and frequency domains, CoRR abs/1808.04022 (2018). arXiv:1808.04022.
URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1808.04022>
- [59] J. Gama, R. P. Ribeiro, S. Mastelini, N. Davarid, B. Veloso, A neuro-symbolic explainer for rare events: A case study on predictive maintenance (2024). arXiv:2404.14455.
URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.14455>
- [60] S. Bobek, G. J. Nalepa, Local universal rule-based explainer (lux), SoftwareX 30 (2025) 102102. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2025.102102>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S235271102500069X>
- [61] L. Feremans, B. Cule, B. Goethals, PETSC: pattern-based embedding for time series classification, Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery 36 (3) (2022) 1015–1061.
- [62] K. Fauvel, T. Lin, V. Masson, É. Fromont, A. Termier, XCM: An explainable convolutional neural network for multivariate time series classification, Mathematics 9 (23) (2021) 3137.

- [63] R. Assaf, I. Giurgiu, F. Bagehorn, A. Schumann, MTEX-CNN: Multivariate Time Series EXplanations for Predictions with Convolutional Neural Networks, in: 2019 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM), 2019, pp. 952–957.
- [64] R. Achibat, M. Dreyer, I. Eisenbraun, S. Bosse, T. Wiegand, W. Samek, S. Lapuschkin, From attribution maps to human-understandable explanations through concept relevance propagation, *Nature Machine Intelligence* 5 (9) (2023) 1006–1019. doi:10.1038/s42256-023-00711-8.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-023-00711-8>
- [65] P. W. Koh, T. Nguyen, Y. S. Tang, S. Mussmann, E. Pierson, B. Kim, P. Liang, Concept bottleneck models, in: *Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Machine Learning*, Vol. 495 of ICML20, JMLR.org, Online, 2020, pp. 5338 – 5348.
- [66] S. Bobek, S. Nowaczyk, J. Gama, S. Pashami, R. P. Ribeiro, Z. Taghiyarrenani, B. Veloso, L. Rajaoarisoa, S. Maciej, Why industry 5.0 needs XAI 2.0?, in: *xAI-2023 Late-breaking Work, Demos and Doctoral Consortium Joint Proceedings*, pp. 1–6.
- [67] L. Longo, M. Brcic, F. Cabitza, J. Choi, R. Confalonieri, J. D. Ser, R. Guidotti, Y. Hayashi, F. Herrera, A. Holzinger, R. Jiang, H. Khosravi, F. Lecue, G. Malgieri, A. Páez, W. Samek, J. Schneider, T. Speith, S. Stumpf, Explainable artificial intelligence (xai) 2.0: A manifesto of open challenges and interdisciplinary research directions, *Information Fusion* 106 (2024) 102301. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2024.102301>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1566253524000794>
- [68] P. F. R. Killick, I. A. Eckley, Optimal detection of changepoints with a linear computational cost, *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 107 (500) (2012) 1590–1598. doi:10.1080/01621459.2012.737745.
- [69] A. Gretton, K. M. Borgwardt, M. J. Rasch, B. Schölkopf, A. Smola, A kernel two-sample test, *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 13 (25) (2012) 723–773.
URL <http://jmlr.org/papers/v13/gretton12a.html>
- [70] P. Fryzlewicz, Wild binary segmentation for multiple change-point detection, *The Annals of Statistics* 42 (6) (2014) 2243–2281.
URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/43556493>
- [71] E. Keogh, S. Chu, D. Hart, M. Pazzani, An online algorithm for segmenting time series, in: *Proceedings 2001 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining*, 2001, pp. 289–296. doi:10.1109/ICDM.2001.989531.
- [72] A. Bifet, R. Gavaldà, Learning from Time-Changing Data with Adaptive Windowing, pp. 443–448. arXiv:<https://epubs.siam.org/doi/pdf/10.1137/1.9781611972771.42>, doi:10.1137/1.9781611972771.42.
URL <https://epubs.siam.org/doi/abs/10.1137/1.9781611972771.42>
- [73] W. Wang, G. Lyu, Y. Shi, X. Liang, Time series clustering based on dynamic time warping, in: *2018 IEEE 9th International Conference on Software Engineering and Service Science (ICSESS)*, 2018, pp. 487–490. doi:10.1109/ICSESS.2018.8663857.

- [74] J. Yang, C. Ning, C. Deb, F. Zhang, D. Cheong, S. E. Lee, C. Sekhar, K. W. Tham, k-shape clustering algorithm for building energy usage patterns analysis and forecasting model accuracy improvement, *Energy and Buildings* 146 (2017) 27–37. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.03.071>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378778817305352>
- [75] M.-B. Jorge, C. Rubén, Time series clustering with random convolutional kernels 38 (4) 1862–1888. doi:[10.1007/s10618-024-01018-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10618-024-01018-x).
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10618-024-01018-x>
- [76] J. Zakaria, A. Mueen, E. Keogh, Clustering time series using unsupervised-shapelets, in: 2012 IEEE 12th International Conference on Data Mining, 2012, pp. 785–794. doi:[10.1109/ICDM.2012.26](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDM.2012.26).
- [77] B. Veloso, R. P. Ribeiro, J. Gama, P. M. Pereira, The MetroPT dataset for predictive maintenance 9 (1) 764, publisher: Nature Publishing Group. doi:[10.1038/s41597-022-01877-3](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01877-3).
URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01877-3>
- [78] F. Mauro, R. Verde, Combining unsupervised and supervised learning techniques for enhancing the performance of functional data classifiers, *Comput. Stat.* 39 (1) (2022) 239–270. doi:[10.1007/s00180-022-01259-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00180-022-01259-8).
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00180-022-01259-8>
- [79] T. W. MacFarland, J. M. Yates, Mann–Whitney U Test, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2016, pp. 103–132. doi:[10.1007/978-3-319-30634-6_4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-30634-6_4).
URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-30634-6_4
- [80] S. Bobek, P. Korycińska, M. Krakowska, M. Mozolewski, D. Rak, M. Zych, M. Wójcik, G. J. Nalepa, Xai-fungi: Dataset from the user study on comprehensibility of xai algorithms (Jul. 2024). doi:[10.5281/zenodo.14980793](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14980793).
URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14980793>
- [81] R. Butz, R. Schulz, A. Hommersom, M. van Eekelen, Investigating the understandability of xai methods for enhanced user experience: When bayesian network users became detectives, *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine* 134 (2022) 102438. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2022.102438>.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S09333365722001907>
- [82] J. Wu, W. Gan, Z. Chen, S. Wan, P. S. Yu, Multimodal large language models: A survey, in: 2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData), 2023, pp. 2247–2256. doi:[10.1109/BigData59044.2023.10386743](https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData59044.2023.10386743).
- [83] M. Bramer, *Avoiding Overfitting of Decision Trees*, Springer London, London, 2013, pp. 121–136. doi:[10.1007/978-1-4471-4884-5_9](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-4884-5_9).
URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-4884-5_9
- [84] I. Sobol’, Global sensitivity indices for nonlinear mathematical models and their monte carlo estimates, *Mathematics and Computers in Simulation* 55 (1) (2001) 271–280, the

Second IMACS Seminar on Monte Carlo Methods. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4754\(00\)00270-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-4754(00)00270-6).
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378475400002706>